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SYNTHESIS OF CHIGARGUNTA GOLD MINES – ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract:

The Chigargunta gold mine is the southern extension of the Kolar gold fields and is situated in the Chittoor district of Andhra Pradesh, Southern India. The rock types encountered in the area include peninsular gneiss, amphibolites, champion gneiss, dykes pegmatites and quartzites. This study was made based on hundred thin sections and twenty five ore mounts that were prepared out of all the rock types collected and a few of chemical analyses in order to know the mineralogical, petrological, petrochemical paragenesis and the nature of metamorphism of rocks and the synthesis as follows.

Synthesis:

Peninsular gneiss consists of quartz, plagioclase, biotites and hornblende. The gneisses are generally migmatitic and heterogeneous in nature and potash metasomatism played a role in their evolution.

The amphibolites are of schistose, granular, massive and fibrous varieties. They consist of quartz, plagioclase, feldspar, hornblende, garnet, sphene, grunerite and iron ore. Quartz belongs to two generations, the older one occurring as round grains within feldspar and later as separate discrete grains that are in contact with feldspar.

The discrete nature of the quartz grains is due to prevailed stress at that time. The presence of the euhedral quartz grains assign a volcanic origin to amphibolites. The amphibole is common hornblende with blue-green tint according to the twin laws of plagioclase feldspar, a metamorphic gneiss can be ascribed to amphibolites. The presence of the garnet is an indication of high temperature origin.

The chemical data of amphibolites, reveals that an increase in SiO_2 , Na_2O and decrease in FeO , CaO , MgO , the increase in al. alk and C and decrease in fm and mg, with increase in Si are the evidence that the amphibolites are formed from crystallization differentiation of basaltic magma.

The diagrammatic representation of the chemical data and the calculated theta (θ) value of 19 reveals the fact that amphibolites are of tholeiite type. They are of middle stage differentiates and show affinity to oceanic tholeiites.

Champion gneiss consists of quartz, K-feldspar, biotite, hornblende, garnet and tourmaline and is considered to be a volcanic origin.

Dykes are the youngest formations in the area. They consist mainly of plagioclase, pyroxene, olivine and iron ore. Dykes are middle stage differentiates having tholeiitic composition, showing affinity to oceanic tholeiites.

Pegmatites are the intrusive rocks and are of complex type. The feldspars of the pegmatites are showing the gliding movement.

The preferred orientation, bending nature of the quartz grains, and the perthitic nature of the feldspars are the diagnostic characters of the quartzites of the areas.

Minute specks of gold have been observed along crystal boundaries and in the interspaces of crystals. The ore minerals include arsenopyrite, pyrrhotite, pyrite, galena, magnetite and alteration of magnetite and alteration of hematite to specularite is found.

The preferred orientation of hornblende, amphibole of blue green tint with higher Al^{+} and Na^{+} K^{+} presence of almandine types of garnet, deformation of the sphene development of cracks in garnet and olivine. Preferred orientation of nature of quartz grains, in some cases bending nature of the quartz grains, and over all mineralogy are the factors to suggest that they are formed under the almandine – amphibolites facies of regional metamorphism.

The close resemblance of the amphibolites and dykes with the oceanic tholeiites is suggestive of the submarine environment in the past.

The brecciated quartz grains, elongation of hornblende grains, garnet with cracks and deformation of sphene in amphibolites, presence of the cracks in olivine and bending pattern of the plagioclase twin lamellae in dykes, gliding movement exhibited by feldspars of the pegmatites, preferred orientation and some cases bending nature of the quartz grains in the quartzites, deformation and fracturing effects in arsenopyrite bending and elongation arrangement of the pyrite crystals are ample evidence to show that tectonism did prevail in the area; but this does not appear to have played a significant role in gold genesis. Hence, it may be possible that the tectonism is not a single episode a part of which is prior to mineralization and other part is later to gold mineralization. While the felsic/mafic minerals are affected by deformation. Arsenic which is occurring as gangue and ore mineral has been found to be the best path finder element for gold deposits.

Gold occurs in native form in conjunction with sulphides in minor quantities. The overall mineralogical characters, high yield of gold from the ore in metallurgical process, the mutual boundary relationship of the gold with sulphides are highly indicative of the premilling type of the ore in the present area.

The association of pyrrhotites, pyrites and galena confirms the vein type of mineralization, which in turn highly suggestive of primary origin.

The Iron-Copper-Gold association assigns that the ore deposits are of hydrothermal sub-group plutonic group and are possibly related to granite suite.

The mineralization is conformed to the isoclinal synform suggests the structural control in the area. Perhaps the tectonic effects observed through direct evidences are highly responsible for the development of folds in the area, and these predate the mineralization.

The presence of the geological thermometers like arsenopyrite, pyrrhotite, garnet, tourmaline, amphibole etc., occurrence of pegmatites; the observed mineralization in metamorphic rocks of Dharwarian age, the structural controls and the persistent effects of extreme pressures are highly confirming the hydrothermal nature of the hydrothermal mineralization.

Mineralization is associated both in mafic and felsic unit. In some times gold mineralization is found to be along crystal boundaries and interspaces of crystals through flow filling and replacement process.

The hydrological data reveals that the weathering and diagnostic process have had a role in mineral alterations. Geological investigations are highly helpful to locate new deposits. A Co-ordinated effort by geologists and botanists helps in exploring the mineral deposits making use of the plant species.

While many author stressed on the greenstones of the archeans as carries of gold in the present study. It is stated that the granitic associates have a longer role to play. It is a very optimal if the granitic associates with the greenstones (both without and those that are concealed) and this will be helpful to locate the mineralization and its mode of origin.

Note: this study is based on the research study of his PhD thesis of the author.